

Supplementary Information

Flexible Piezoresistive Polystyrene Composite Sensors Filled with Hollow 3D Graphitic Shells

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Figure S1. Change of resistance as a function of bending for GS/PS (a), CNT/PS (b). Results obtained by commercially available DPM Solid multimeter.

Figure S2. Change of resistance as a function of elongation for PS/3D-Graphene. Results obtained by commercially available DPM Solid multimeter.